

Analysis of COVID-19 Swab Statistics

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Abstract

Each day during the current COVID-19 pandemic many countries report the number of diagnostic swabs performed and the number of positive cases found. These data help to predict the immediate course of the public health emergency. However, their interpretation is non-trivial because the more tests performed, the greater the number of positive cases that will be found. In this document we propose a method for interpreting the data and we apply it to data from Italy.

Introduction

The current COVID-19 pandemic is overwhelming the health services of many countries. One of the countries most affected in Europe is Italy, a country for which fairly reliable data are available. Daily statistics are provided by the Dipartimento della Protezione Civile and are freely available for download [1]. The relevant file is “dpc-covid19-ita-regioni.csv”. Figure 1 plots the daily number of inpatients (the column labelled “totale_ospedalizzati” in the CSV file) summed for all regions. The numbers are now rising again, but will this continue?

The data file contains various other parameters, in particular the number of nasal swabs performed and the number of new cases detected. However, as more swabs are performed, more cases are detected and this makes interpretation problematic. We have previously proposed a severity statistic based on a partial ordering derived from the number of new cases and the proportion of positive swabs [2]. In the rest of this document we propose an alternative approach that exploits the considerable weekly oscillation in both swabs performed and new cases detected: see Figures 2 and 3. We suggest an empirical model that relates the number of swabs performed each day and the number of new cases. We use the same methods as in our previous paper to deal with the small number of anomalies in the data.

Figure 1: *Number of COVID-19 inpatients in Italy in the period 24/02/2020 to 11/03/2021.*

Figure 2: *Daily number of swabs performed in the period 24/02/2020 to 11/03/2021.*

Figure 3: *Daily number of new cases of COVID-19 in the period 24/02/2020 to 11/03/2021.*

Model

On any given day, let s be the number of swabs performed and let c be the number of new cases detected. Furthermore, let C be the total number of new cases that would have been detected had the entire population, excluding previously-detected cases, been tested. Our first assumption is a weak one: for any given C , the expected number of new cases depends only on the number of swabs carried out.

Assumption 1 (Weak Dependence) *The expected number of newly detected cases c on any given day is uniquely determined by s and C .*

Consider now how the expected value of c varies with s for constant C . It depends on the testing strategy. If testing were performed by randomly selecting a subset of the population each day to swab (excluding known cases) then c would be directly proportional to s . However, in practice the set of persons tested each day comprises several distinct subsets with different case prevalences and different priorities for testing. For example,

1. Sick patients who require admission to hospital and who are strongly suspected of having COVID-19.
2. Suspected COVID-19 cases that seem suitable for management in the community.
3. Persons undergoing precautionary screening such as international travellers.
4. Concerned persons who are anxious to verify that they do not have COVID-19 before, say, visiting friends and family.

If testing resources are limited then it is the first of these groups that are prioritized for testing. Therefore, for any given C , the greater the number of swabs performed (s), the lower the expected yield of positive cases (c/s). This means that the functional dependence of c on s is convex upwards; its gradient, while remaining non-negative, decreases as s increases.

Now, we make some further assumptions before deriving from them a stronger modelling assumption.

1. If C increases then various subgroups do not change their constitution, only their size.
2. If C increases by a given factor then the size of each of the various subgroups increases by the same factor.
3. If both C and s increase by the same factor then the priority for distributing the tests among the various subgroups does not change.

It thus follows that as C varies, the expected c/s and the gradient dc/ds remain constant. These collectively amount to a stronger assumption.

Assumption 2 (Strong Dependence) *The expected gradient dc/ds depends only on the expected fraction c/s .*

The nature of this dependence embodies the testing strategy, in other words the policy for prioritizing the testing of the various subgroups given their size and the amount of testing resources available. We refer to this as the *characteristic function*, ϕ .

$$\frac{dc}{ds} = \phi\left(\frac{c}{s}\right) \quad (1)$$

Characteristic Function ϕ

The marked weekly oscillation that we see in s and c (Figures 2 and 3), while unhelpfully obfuscating the trend of the pandemic, paradoxically reveals function ϕ . On each day we determine dc/ds by least-squares linear regression over the seven days comprising the given day, its three predecessors and its three successors. We cannot do this for the first three days or the last three days of the time series because either they do not have three predecessors or they do not have three successors. Therefore, for expediency, we simply assume that the gradient does not change during the first four days or during the last four days.

Figure 4 plots the calculated gradient against the fraction c/s . There is considerable scatter, but dc/ds appears to be proportional to c/s . Thus, for some constant of proportionality α ,

$$\frac{dc}{ds} = \alpha \left(\frac{c}{s}\right) \quad (2)$$

Estimating α each day as $(dc/ds) \div (c/s)$, Figure 5 plots the daily estimate. Although there is considerable variation, there is no marked trend, so a constant value should suffice.

The general solution of the first-order homogeneous differential equation is

$$c = ks^\alpha \quad (3)$$

where k is an arbitrary value that is independent of c and s but which is free to vary with time. We refer to it as the *severity* of the pandemic. If the model is correct and the value chosen for α is optimum then the severity should not show any weekly oscillation. We quantify the variation as proportional to the sum of square differences between successive values, half a week apart. We normalize by the sum of square severities so that the error is independent of scale. Let the severities calculated for each day in the time series be $k_0, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{n-1}$ where currently $n = 382$. We define the error E to be

$$E = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{n-5} (2k_i - k_{i+3} - k_{i+4})^2}{\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} k_i^2} \quad (4)$$

Figure 6 plots this error over a range of possible values of α . Minimum error occurs when $\alpha = 0.6139$. The corresponding plots for this optimum value are shown in red in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 7 plots the daily values of k for optimum α . Clearly there is some visible weekly oscillation, most marked in recent weeks. No doubt more sophisticated modelling of the characteristic function would suppress this further. However, a simple way to improve the graph is to smooth the plot.

Figure 4: Plot of dc/ds against c/s in the period 24/02/2020 to 11/03/2021.

Figure 5: *Plot of α in the period 24/02/2020 to 11/03/2021.*

Figure 6: Plot of error E against α for the period 24/02/2020 to 11/03/2021.

Figure 7: *Severity (k) in the period 24/02/2020 to 11/03/2021.*

Smoothing

We first apply the logarithmic transformation $\log(x+1)$ to stabilize cycle amplitude. We then filter weekly oscillation from the severity in the conventional manner by using a centrally-aligned, seven-day, moving-average filter. We use the method described in [3] to handle the first three days and the last three days, thus avoiding any truncation of the time series. We apply the inverse logarithmic transformation after smoothing.

Figure 8 (page 12) shows the results. There appear to be nearly twice as many cases during the second wave compared to the first. Worryingly, the recovery from the second wave has stalled and reversed. This is now reflected in the number of hospital inpatients (Figure 1); the severity statistic anticipates the change in inpatient numbers by more than a week.

Furthermore, the severity statistic (k) allows a crude estimate to be made of C , the total number of active cases. This is calculated by assuming that the entire population (currently 60461826) is subjected to a swab. For example, maximum severity ($k = 18.66$) occurred on 13/11/2020. Thus, on that day we estimate the total number of cases to be

$$\begin{aligned} C &= 18.66 \times 60461826^{0.6139} \\ &= 1116367 \end{aligned}$$

This roughly corresponds to the maximum number of active cases in Italy (805944) reported by the Worldometer website [4]. According to that website this maximum was reached on 22/11/2020, nine days later than according to our data, but this may be due to delays in reporting.

Discussion

The severity score is a general guide to the relative progression of the pandemic. It anticipates the number of hospital inpatients by more than a week and hence the changing pressure on hospital services. Although it is harder to interpret in absolute terms than the conventional reproduction number [5], the latter entails various modelling assumptions, is complicated to calculate, and is normally expressed with often wide error bounds. By contrast, the severity statistic is easy to calculate and requires only the daily numbers of new cases and swabs performed.

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Figure 8: *Smoothed plot of severity (k) in the period 24/02/2020 to 11/03/2021.*

References

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